

ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH MEDIA TECHNOLOGIES: A FOCUS ON ENGLISH EDUCATION FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The integration of media technology in English language education has become essential in improving grammatical competence, particularly for A1 level students. This article explores the use of modern pedagogical methods, media tools, and computer-based programs in teaching English in primary school classrooms. It highlights the role of media technology in enhancing students' imagination, increasing retention and developing individual abilities. By utilizing multimedia materials such as videos, audio and graphics, teachers can create engaging and effective lessons. The implementation of media technologies aligns with global trends in education, contributing to a more interactive and personalized learning experience for young learners.

Key words: Media, media technology, media pedagogy, information tools, advanced pedagogical technologies, multimedia

The global socio-economic changes taking place in the world, the process of integration requires the development of the system of teaching foreign languages as a priority in general secondary education. In English classes, special attention is paid to the development of students' grammatical competence on the basis of media technologies, and the use of modern pedagogical technologies in foreign language teaching. In the studies, it is recognized that the development of linguistic competence of students in foreign languages in secondary schools, especially in English, based on an integrative approach, is of scientific and methodological importance. The experience of developed countries also proves that it is a priority to have knowledge, skills and competence about grammar listed in the educational content of English language teaching, especially for A1 levels, and to be able to use it in speech.

The 44th goal of the Presidential Decree no. 60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" focuses on improving the quality of education in schools and bringing the knowledge and skills of pedagogues to international level [Presidential decree, 2022. - 23]. Today, teaching foreign languages from primary school in Europe is not as popular as in our Republic, but it is an important direction of language policy. In European countries, when introducing a foreign language subject to the primary school program (children aged 5-6 to 10-11 years old), teachers follow the recommendations developed within the framework of the European Union "Language learning for European citizenship" and as a result, in teaching a foreign language European countries are making a lot of progress.

Currently, in our republic, it requires the necessity of implementation based on searching, finding and experiment with new factors to accustom elementary school students to school. In teaching English and adapting to education at school, children's mental preparation, being physically healthy, able to communicate, enriching their vocabulary (word-stock), acquiring basic elementary concepts, primary preparation for writing and knowledge of concepts about certain words play an important role. Especially 7-10 years old children have a great need for information. In this regard, the use of media technologies in teaching English is important for all children who are brought up in educational institutions. At this time, increasing the child's opportunities to get used to it, expanding his social relations, is of great importance for the formation of the child's personality. In this regard, it is written in the encyclopedic dictionary that "it is important in the upbringing, education and development of children as a means of psychologically preparing them for the future life" [Explanatory dictionary, 1976. - 232]. These are general definitions of the use of media technologies and describe the essence of media technology.

Problems related to the methodology of teaching foreign languages in general secondary schools in our country, the development of grammatical competence, which is considered a component of linguistic competence in English, its role and importance in language learning, as well as the use of an integrative approach in teaching English, on the scientific-theoretical issues of using media technologies in the lesson have been studied by the scientists of our republic J.J. Jalolov, G.Kh. Bakieva, L.T. Ahmedova, T.Q. Sattorov, H.T. Mustafaeva, I.M. Tokhtasinov, M.Sh. Ruzmetova, M.A. Abdullaeva, A.A. Isakov, N.M. Abdullaeva and M.Kh. Gulyamova in their scientific works.

In addition to the traditional opportunities, the advancing informational tools in our society determine the basis of social development, as well as factors such as people's ability, initiative, creative approach to work, intellectual activity, independent improvement of their knowledge and skills. The process of creating information related to the storage, transmission, and reception of large amounts of information provides for the development of computer technologies in various fields of human activity.

Today, the wide possibilities of using multimedia tools in education have already been confirmed.

There are different opinions about the concept of media technology, and it is noted in the American International Encyclopedia of Society that "media technology" is the ability of a person to be active and literate, to be able to receive and create media texts, to analyze and evaluate, to understand the sociocultural and political content of modern media while feeling his responsibility as a citizen in society [International encyclopedia, 2001. - 9494].

Media includes the system of print, press, television, cinematography, radio, sound recording and the Internet. G.A.Polichko, A.V.Fedorov, R.G.Rabinovich, Y.M.Rabinovich and others among the scientists who have studied and analyzed the direction of media education, studying the form and methods of work revealed the pedagogical and methodical importance of media technologies.

To the problems such as teaching English based on media technologies, developing students' speech, oral and grammatical competences with the help of informational tools during the lesson, developing new teaching methods, using advanced pedagogical technologies, computer technologies in classes and didactic design of lessons a serious attention is being paid.

Today, when the processes of globalization are accelerating all over the world, modern communication technologies serve as an important factor in the further improvement of the education sector in our country. Nowadays, almost all educational institutions in our country are equipped with computers. This technology performs millions of tasks every second. Among them, there are also many programs that serve for media technology. Therefore, its effective use in the further improvement of the education sector is the demand of our era. Media-related terms can be studied by conventionally dividing into 6 directions: television, film, radio, advertising, Internet, new media and press.

Media technology comes from the English word media "education" and as the Latin word media means factor. Media technology requires the use of new methods in the process of teaching students.

The main goal of media education consists of forming skills like helping to understand the basic laws, learning the language of media information in simple directions, contributing to the artistic growth and development of the student, receiving, studying and competently analyzing media texts. Globalization in the field of information is creating a basis for the formation of a new worldview.

As modern knowledge improves, the problem of correct and effective use of information is emerging. Currently, it is almost impossible to control the content of information, as well as the methods and ways of its distribution through mass media networks. So, in order to avoid any confusion and mistakes in this matter, a perfect system is necessary. This system depends on the high level of knowledge and their correct understanding of each other of the information distributor and its consumer. Now, some specialists are looking for ways to correctly form information in the mind of the student, so to speak, to organize it systematically. In the educational practices of developed countries of the world, research in this field began in the 70s of the last century. This created the basis for the emergence of a unique direction as media technology in the science of pedagogy.

Media technology requires the use of new methods in the process of teaching students.

Media pedagogy is a new pedagogical technology that allows creative thinking and education with the help of mass media. The resources of media pedagogy include information on the Internet, television, radio broadcasts, film, video, and audio materials.

In the conditions of today's globalization, the issue of using media technology in teaching a foreign language in the primary classes of general education schools is significant. Modern programs, teaching methods, methods, telecommunication tools and mass media are developing at a rapid pace. Therefore, the methodology of teaching English such as the definition of didactic requirements for the integration to education of media information, software-pedagogical tools and multimedia training manuals in the field of all teaching methods, media technology in teaching English and analysis of usage of methods of information technology, is important.

Education based on media technology arouses lively interest of students in the primary class and allows developing the individual abilities of each child and increasing the activity of knowledge. The importance of media technology is not based on the reaction of children, but the effectiveness of the lesson increases by seeing and hearing specific tasks applied to each child. It should be noted that there is a large network of didactic games, but there is no clear classification of them. We offer broad classifications of media technologies in science, which are intended for use in the process of teaching elementary school students to communicate in English (Fig. 1).

Organization of educational activities based on media technology using media tools and computer programs helps to present the studied materials in a more clear and understandable way and to increase the imagination of students to a great extent. It is known that in the "Guess What" textbook of the English language in the primary classes, students can have problems connected to imagination. The reason for this is that not all students have the same ability of imagination and perception. If we use special QR-coded topics in this section for who uses video electronic programs and manuals as a media tool, we will achieve an increase in the student's imagination and a more solid place in his memory. Apart from this, computer-based teaching and computer-based modeling of objects in the subject save class

Figure 1. Classification of the use of media technologies in teaching English to A1 level students.

time and facilitate the process of teacher's preparation for the lesson.

It is possible to save up to 30% of time in acquiring knowledge on the basis of media technology tools, and the acquired knowledge is retained in the memory for a long time. If the students receive the given materials on the basis of viewing (video), the retention of information in memory increases by 25-30%. In addition to this, when learning materials are presented in the form of audio, video and graphics, the retention of the materials increases by 75% [Ganieva, 2023. - 87].

The following information on media education and its importance in the educational process is given in the research:

- integrated and interdisciplinary study of media in the curriculum;
- studies that the "media topic" is analyzed within a specific discipline;
- a critical approach to the media through practical work and analysis;
- its form, technologies and methods of information transmission;
- media agencies, their social, political and cultural role;
- the impact of media on audiences through language and art [Kholliiev, 2022. - 97].

In conclusion, when the educational process is organized using specially prepared multimedia applications, videos and various animation materials during the lesson, it increases students' interest in the subject in the formation of practical thinking and imagination and creates an opportunity for them to quickly understand. Also, it is advisable to organize moments of musical rest during the lesson so that students do not get tired and bored. Similarly, the use of media education in English language classes in elementary grades further develops students' logical thinking and present-responsibility skills.

In the process of teaching English in the primary classes of general secondary schools providing with media materials and forming by the use of information and communication tools (setting educational issues, determining the content of practical subjects, showing samples on the implementation of each individual action, monitoring the performance of each action and evaluating whether the issue has been resolved or completed) are continuous and sequential processes.

As a conclusion, it is worth noting that media technology provides an "attractive" lesson in the formation of a favorable psychological climate for young students and diversification of the lesson. It is in foreign language classes and in extracurricular activities that the cooperative skills of students are formed in the shape of the "teacher-student" scheme by using media forms of activity. The introduction of media technologies in conducting foreign language classes in elementary grades leads to the formation of a psychological climate that develops students' interest in the lesson.

REFERENCES

1. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language Tashkent.: Science. 1976. -P. 232.
 2. Ganieva G. SITUATION OF MEDIA EDUCATION OF SCIENCE TEACHING IN PRIMARY CLASS. Proceedings of International Educators Conference Hosted online from Rome, Italy. Date: 25th January, 2023.
 3. International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences. Vol. 14 / Eds.N.J.Smelser & P.B.Baltes. Oxford, 2001, p.9494.
 4. Kholiev A. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 7 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337.
 5. [PD-no. 60- 28.01.2022. On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 \(lex.uz\)](#)
 6. Зарликов И., Болтабоева А. Значение и эффективность новых технологий в обучении иностранному языку //Ренессанс в парадигме новаций образования и технологий в XXI веке. – 2022. – №. 1. – С. 184-185.
<https://doi.org/10.47689/innovations-in-edu-vol-iss1-pp184-185>
 7. Urazimbetova , G., & Aytbaeva, M. (2023). ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK TOPONYMIC PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LINGUISTICS. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(6), 200–202. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/16868>
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8023020>
 8. Зарликов И., Айтбаева М. Media technologies in the english lesson as a technical tool and media education // Ренессанс в парадигме новаций образования и технологий в XXI веке. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 52-56.
<https://doi.org/10.47689/XXIA-TTIPR-vol1-iss1-pp52-56>
 9. Зарликов, И. (2024). Mechanisms of formation of speech skills on the basis of media technologies. *Актуальные вопросы лингвистики и преподавания иностранных языков: достижения и инновации*, 1(1), 274–277.
<https://doi.org/10.47689/TOPICAL-TILTFL-vol1-iss1-2024-pp274-277>
 10. Zarlikov, I. (2024). INTEGRATING MEDIA TECHNOLOGIES TO ENHANCE LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN A1 LEVEL LEARNERS. *Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarni tadbiq etishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari va rivojlanish omillari*, 34(1), 3-8.
 11. <https://pedagoglar.org/index.php/01/article/view/4738>
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